

Relative incidence of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) in *Bt* and their corresponding non *Bt* cotton genotypes

VIJANDER PAL, P. D. SHARMA, RAHUL CHAUHAN AND S. L. JAT

Department of Entomology, CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar-125 004

ABSTRACT : Performance of eight *Bt* and non *Bt* cotton genotypes for American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) infestation and its larval population was evaluated at Research Farm of CCS Haryana Agricultural University, Hisar. The infestation due to American bollworm and its larval population was nil in *Bt* cotton genotypes both under unprotected and protected conditions. The infestation in non *Bt* genotypes under unprotected conditions was maximum in RCH 134 (2.39%) and minimum in RCH 317 (0.88%), while under protected conditions it was maximum in ANKUR 651 (0.67%) and minimum in RCH 317 (0.10%). The larval population in non *Bt* genotypes was recorded maximum in ANKUR 2534 (1.24) and minimum in RCH 134 (0.52) under unprotected conditions. However, under protected conditions, the larval population was recorded maximum in RCH 138 (0.89) and minimum in ANKUR 651 (0.33). The maximum yield in *Bt* genotype was recorded in RCH 134 (27.84 and 30.04 q/ha) under unprotected and protected conditions, respectively. While in non *Bt* genotypes, maximum yield in ANKUR 2226 (12.75 q/ha) under unprotected conditions and in RCH 134 (25.37 q/ha) under protected conditions was recorded.

Key words : American bollworm, *Bt* and non *Bt* cotton genotypes, protected and unprotected conditions

India is amongst the major cotton growing countries of the world and ranks 1st in global scenario (about 20% of the world cotton area) by growing cotton on 8.5-9.0 million hectare, but productivity-wise the country ranks 2nd after China by producing 31.5 million bales during 2007-2008 (Anonymous, 2008). The heavy attack of bollworm pests and ineffective control measures, conventional use of insecticides resulted in decreased total productivity and also production in cotton. The insect-pests are known to cause 56-60 per cent reduction in yield (Sharma, 1998) but during favourable weather (medium temperature and relative humidity) the damage may reach any height.

Among the insects of economic importance, spotted bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd) and *Earias vittella* (Fab.), American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) and pink bollworm, *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) are the most important and have been reported to cause serious quantitative and qualitative losses. The number of sprays to control these pests may range from 5 to 15 or more with an all India average of seven sprays per cotton cropping season. In Indian agriculture 54 per cent insecticides are applied only in cotton, which are estimated to about Rs. 1600 crores for the control of cotton pests and out of this Rs. 1200 crores against bollworms alone (Armes *et al.*, 1996). At present in India, *Bt* cotton is grown over 7.6

million hectare out of 9.6 million hectare of total cotton area. Use of *Bt* cotton reduced the usage of insecticide (Mohan and Manjunath, 2002).

The studies were carried out to compare the relative performance of *Bt* cotton hybrids for infestation from American bollworm and its larval population in comparison with its non *Bt* counterparts at CCS Haryana Agricultural University Farm during *kharif* 2003. The experiment was conducted in randomized block design under unprotected and protected conditions testing eight *Bt* hybrids (ANKUR 651 *Bt*, RCH 134 *Bt*, MRC 6301 *Bt*, ANKUR 2226 *Bt*, RCH 138 *Bt*, ANKUR 2534 *Bt*, MRC 6304 *Bt* and RCH 317 *Bt*) and their corresponding non *Bt* hybrids. Each treatment was replicated three times. Under unprotected conditions no insecticidal intervention was made, whereas in protected conditions the recommended insecticides were applied on the basis of economic threshold level. The data were recorded at weekly interval for per cent bollworm infestation. The total intact and shed fruiting bodies from five plants of each treatment were taken into consideration. The larval population was also recorded from five plants/treatment. The yield from all the genotypes was also recorded.

As per weekly observations recorded, the American bollworm infestation and its larval population noticed from 32nd standard week

onwards were nil in all the *Bt* genotypes both under unprotected and protected conditions. In non *Bt* genotypes under unprotected conditions, maximum infestation was in RCH 134 (2.39%) and ANKUR 2226 (1.90%) and minimum in RCH 317 (0.88%) and MRC 6301 (1.09%). Under protected conditions, it was maximum in ANKUR 651 (0.67%) and RCH 134 (0.57%) and minimum in MRC 6304 (0.10%) and RCH 317 (0.10%).

The American bollworm larval population under unprotected conditions was maximum in ANKUR 2534 (1.24) and MRC 6304 (1.16), and minimum in RCH 134 (0.52) and MRC 6301 (0.59). Under protected conditions, it was maximum in RCH 138 (0.89) and ANKUR 2534 (0.82) and minimum in Ankur 651 (0.33) and RCH 317 (0.34) (Table 1). The present results that *Bt*

genotypes did not have any *Helicoverpa* infestation are supported by the work of Cui *et al.* (2000) and Sun *et al.* (2002). They studied the population dynamics of main pests and reported that *Bt* cotton was highly resistant to American bollworm, *H. armigera* and its peak larval population was significantly smaller than those of non *Bt* cotton.

Under unprotected conditions the *Bt* genotypes RCH 134 *Bt* (27.84 q/ha) and RCH 317 *Bt* (25.09 q/ha) yielded maximum, while amongst non *Bt* genotypes ANKUR 2226 (12.75 q/ha) and ANKUR 2534 (11.38 q/ha) produced higher. Under protected conditions, *Bt* genotypes RCH 134 *Bt* (30.04 q/ha), RCH 317 *Bt* (27.57 q/ha) and in non *Bt* genotypes RCH 134 (25.37 q/ha) and RCH 138 (21.39 q/ha) yielded higher (Table 2). The present

Table 1. Relative incidence (%) and larval population of American bollworm, *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner) in *Bt* and their corresponding non *Bt* genotypes, under unprotected and protected conditions during kharif 2003

Genotype	Mean* infestation (%) and larval population of <i>Helicoverpa armigera</i>							
	Unprotected condition				Protected condition			
	Infestation (%)		Larval population/plant		Infestation (%)		Larval population/plant	
	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>
ANKUR 651	0.0	1.21	0.0	0.85	0.0	0.67	0.0	0.33
RCH 134	0.0	2.39	0.0	0.52	0.0	0.57	0.0	0.79
MRC 6301	0.0	1.09	0.0	0.59	0.0	0.33	0.0	0.57
ANKUR 2226	0.0	1.90	0.0	1.03	0.0	0.22	0.0	0.57
RCH 138	0.0	1.14	0.0	0.84	0.0	0.43	0.0	0.89
ANKUR 2534	0.0	1.80	0.0	1.24	0.0	0.35	0.0	0.82
MRC 6304	0.0	1.26	0.0	1.16	0.0	0.10	0.0	0.65
RCH 317	0.0	0.88	0.0	0.78	0.0	0.10	0.0	0.34
Mean	0.0	1.46	0.0	0.88	0.0	0.35	0.0	0.62

*Means of nine weeks (32nd-41st standard weeks, 6 August-14 October).

Table 2. Yield in *Bt* and non *Bt* genotypes under unprotected and protected conditions during kharif 2003

Genotype	Yield of seed cotton (q/ha)			
	Unprotected conditions		Protected conditions	
	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>	<i>Bt</i>	Non <i>Bt</i>
ANKUR 651	19.20	10.01	19.89	18.92
RCH 134	27.84	9.46	30.04	25.37
MRC 6301	18.65	6.30	23.59	18.92
ANKUR 2226	17.28	12.75	20.43	19.06
RCH 138	21.12	4.66	26.47	21.39
ANKUR 2534	13.71	11.38	20.71	19.61
MRC 6304	15.35	5.24	18.65	10.69
RCH 317	25.09	8.22	27.57	16.59
Mean	19.78	8.50	23.42	18.82

studies support the findings of Khadi and Kulkarni (1998) as well as Qaim and Zilberman (2002). They carried out farm field trials with *Bacillus thuringiensis* (*Bt* cotton) in different states of India and showed that the *Bt* technology substantially reduced pest damage and increased yield.

REFERENCES

- Anonymous, 2008. All India Co-coordinated Cotton Improvement Project Annual Report. CICR, Nagpur. pp. 1-2.
- Armes, N. S., Jadhav, D. R. and Desouza, K. R. 1996. A survey of insecticide resistance in *Helicoverpa armigera* in Indian sub-continent.

- Bull. Entomol. Res.* **86** : 499-514.
- Cui, J. J. and Xia, J. Y. 2000.** Effects of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) transgenic cotton on the dynamics of pest population and their enemies. *Acta Phytophylacica Sinica* **27** : 141-45.
- Khadi, B. M. and Kulkarni, V. N. 1998.** Future research needs for improving yields and qualities of farmers under rainfed conditions. Proceeding National Seminar "Strategies for Improvement of Production, Productivity and Quality of Cotton", Mumbai, 4-5 May. pp. 14.
- Mohan, K. S. and Manjunath, T. M. 2002.** Bt cotton India's first transgenic crop. *J. Pl. Bio.* **29** : 225-36.
- Qaim, M. and Zilberman, D. 2002.** Yield effects of genetically modified crops in developing countries. *Science*. Washington. pp. 900-02.
- Sharma, P. D. 1998.** Estimation of yield losses due to insect-pests on cotton. Annual Report of All India Co-ordinated Cotton Improvement Project, 1997-1998, CCSHAU, Hisar.
- Sun, J., Tang, C. M., Zhu, X. F., Guo, W. Z., Zhang, T. Z., Zhou, W. J., Meng, F. X. and Sheng, J. L. 2002.** Characterization of resistance to *Helicoverpa armigera* in three lines of transgenic Bt upland cotton. *Euphytica* **123** : 343-51.

Received for publication : October 5, 2009